

REFLECTIVE PORTFOLIO: AN EDUCATIONAL TOOL IN SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL BIOLOGY INSTRUCTION

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Reflective Portfolio: An Educational Tool in Senior High School Biology Instruction

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Abstract

This action research investigated the effectiveness of reflective portfolio approach in biology instruction among Science and Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) learners in the hope of contributing to the corpus of knowledge already available on successful teaching strategies. This study made use of action research approach using both quantitative and qualitative methods of research involving forty (40) Grade 12 STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) Senior High School learners. A validated 40-item multiple-choice questionnaire served as the pre-test and post-test for the participants to gauge their understanding of biology topics (Cell Theory, Cell structure, and function) before and after intervention as quantitative data for the study. For qualitative data, a journal was utilized to gather qualitative data from the FGD and interview. The quantitative results revealed that before the instruction using the reflective portfolio, the pre-test scores of the participants were average, while after the implementation of the intervention, the post-test scores of the participants showed a high result. Furthermore, their pre-test and post-test scores in their level of understanding of Biology topics showed a significant difference in the level of understanding of Biology topics. Qualitative data from interviews and focus group discussions also revealed that reflective portfolios improve learners' performance in Biology topics by encouraging critical thinking, promoting deeper understanding, encouraging problem-solving skills, and increasing learners' engagement. The study concludes that reflective portfolios serve as an effective pedagogical tool in biology instruction, fostering a deeper understanding of the subject matter and promoting continuous improvement in the learning practices.

Keywords: *reflection, portfolio, educational tool, biology instruction*

Introduction

Within the academic realm, science is one of the oldest and most important subjects covering a wide topic. This subject is crucial for the advancement of the country because of its ties to industry and technology. It assists students in developing the skills necessary for scientific inquiry, morality, and attitudes such as objectivity, curiosity, and honesty, as well as mental habits such as critical thinking, all of which are advantageous to each student's personal development, future career aspirations, and general well-being (SEI-DOST & UP NISMED in 2011).

Science is further divided into different difficult discipline Even though Biology is a essential subject, it is considered as one of the difficult subject for learners. The perceived complexity of this subjects among learners could be is due to several factors. These factors varies like memorizing significant information, such as terminology, procedures, and the names and roles of biological structures, adds to the complexity of the subject and necessitates a profound comprehension of the many concepts and their linkages (Chiepetta & Fillman, 1998). It is a discipline that requires a strong background knowledge in other STEM fields like chemistry, physics, and mathematics to understand which makes it an interdisciplinary discipline. (Lazarowitz and Penso,1992). Biology is a subject that usually deals with abstract ideas and processes that is happening at the microscopic level which makes it hard to see and comprehend. It is also one of the experimental science that requires practical skills and laboratory work (Çimer, 2004). In doing research in this field it usually carries out tests, evaluating information, and interpreting findings are essential steps (Çimer, 2007).

According to Ogunkola and Clifford (2013), biology curriculum distinguishes between the functions of science and technology in day-to-day human endeavors. This has been an important topic for the growth and development of a country in recent years. As a result, the performance of learners in this topic is being tracked often across the globe (Bietenback, 2011), and it is becoming a concern for all countries (Villarino, 2020).

It's not simple to understand the things covered in biology classes. The students' low academic achievement serves as evidence for it (Hasibuan & Djulia, 2017). It's also true that students from other nations have reported difficulties in their biology classes. Çimer (2012), for instance, found that learning about the material cycle, endocrine system, aerobic respiration, cell division, genes, and chromosomes was challenging for Turkish pupils. According to the other survey results, which were also carried out in Turkey, physiology, genetics, and cytology were classified as challenging biological subjects (Gungor & Ozkan, 2017). In a similar vein, Etobro and Fabinu's (2017) study revealed that Nigerian students had trouble understanding certain biology concepts.

The Philippines is one of the nations with issues with high school biology academic performance in the contemporary global knowledge environment, which is dominated by science and technology (Capuno et al., 2019; OECD, 2020; Bell, 2013). Villarino (2023) strongly recommends teachers to carefully plan and supply the proper learning activities based on the needs and knowledge gaps of the students in their instructional practices to ensure that their students fully understand the subject taught in biology class.

Numerous recent studies have demonstrated that standard biology teaching strategies frequently fall short of promoting critical thinking

and a thorough comprehension of intricate biological concepts. As a biology teacher, the researcher is interested of using many alternative pedagogical approaches that have been established for teaching the subject to close the gap. One of the strategy he proposed is the use of reflective portfolio. The most crucial educational exercise for improving comprehension abilities is reflection, which is mostly experienced-based. Emsheimer (2005) asserts that reflection is more than just regular "thinking." Reflection aims to apply information by creating new cognitive patterns and looking for answers to various problems. As a result, reflection is a continuous process that involves attitudes, knowledge, abilities, and insight for improving one's abilities. It is important to follow a methodical and well-defined structure while implementing reflection.

By critically analyzing and reflecting on its contents, reflective portfolios are described as the compilation of evidence attesting to accomplishment as well as professional and personal development. According to McMullan, Endacott, Gray, Jasper, Miller, and Scholes (2003), the reflective portfolio differs from other fields' "showcasing of best work" approach by requiring the applicant to engage in reflection. Reflective portfolios have been used for formative and summative assessments, curriculum development, authentic assessment, bridging the "theory-practice divide," and adopting a deep rather than a surface approach to learning, among other uses. According to Ediger (2000) and Tiwari and Tang (2003), reflective portfolios have been proposed as a more constructivist method of evaluating student learning because they allow students to choose and compile evidence of meeting course and learning objectives as well as the accompanying justification of inclusion based on those objectives.

When using the reflective portfolio technique, student learning is assessed using data from a carefully curated collection of their work that demonstrates accomplishment, development, growth, and reflection. Portfolios are referred to as evidence containers. These concepts clarify that for students to demonstrate their learning, they must perform tasks requiring them to apply and employ their knowledge (Villarino, 2023).

Therefore, by investigating the reflective portfolio approach in biology education, the study aims to add to the corpus of knowledge already available on successful teaching strategies. Through examining reflection's function and how it affects students' learning, this study offers insightful information about the advantages and ramifications of using a portfolio approach in biology education. Finally, by using the study's findings, curriculum designers and educators can create biology lessons that are both more interesting and productive.

Methodology

Methods

The action research method particularly the one-group pre-test-post-test design was used in this investigation. However, since numbers couldn't justify the instruments used enough, mixed methods were employed to understand the research completely; thus, interviews, focused-group discussion (FGD), and researchers' journals were used. For the interview for FGD, an open-ended guide questionnaire was formulated.

Subjects

The forty (40) Grade 12 Senior High School learners enrolled in a high school in a municipality in Calinog, Province of Iloilo, Philippines, who were studying STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) were the study's participants. They were also chosen since the proponent was also their subject teacher.

Instruments

Multiple Choice Questionnaire. A 40-item multiple-choice questionnaire designed by the researcher specifically for General Biology subjects was used in this investigation. This was validated by experts from the municipality of Calinog, Iloilo in Region VI, Western Visayas, the Philippines, including master teachers and head teachers of science. Drafts of the questionnaire were sent to the expert panel for validation of the face and content, as well as an inspection of each item to ensure that it was relevant, proper, and significant for the particular inference. The tool were refined taking into account the advice, modifications, and suggestions of the specialists. This was then administered for reliability testing to 50 students who belong to one section of the selected school and who were not included in the study. The results underwent item analysis to determine which items would be retained, revised, or rejected.

This served as the pre-test and post-test for the participants to gauge their understanding of biology topics (Cell Theory, Cell structure, and function) before and after intervention. This was quantitative raw data for the study.

Journal. A journal was utilized for the mixed technique, which concentrates on qualitative components. From the FGD and interview were conducted to determine the experience of the participants in the use of reflective portfolio as an intervention. The researchers also made use of observation. These were all recorded by the researcher. The data obtained from the participants was held confidential for security purposes.

Intervention

This action research made use of "Reflective Portfolio" as the intervention.

Reflective Portfolio. is a collection of essays that condenses the knowledge and understanding that a student has acquired from a practical task. It is intended to evaluate the student's involvement in their fieldwork as well as their application of academic knowledge in a practical situation. The portfolio itself can be a long-written piece, a notebook or binder containing brief writings and supporting documentation, or an online collection of these types of works (Davis, Ponnampuruma & Ker, 2009).

The reflective portfolio allows students to examine their own learning process, which sets it apart from standard coursework. In contrast to standard academic assignments, which require students to be impersonal and objective, a reflective portfolio allows students to emphasize their own unique viewpoints, thoughts, and emotions. It offers a truthful synopsis of the tasks completed and the skill sets acquired. Authentic participation in the course material is more important for success than just being able to get good marks on tests or essays.

In this study, reflective portfolio were given as enhancement activity for the learners. They were ask to answer the given sets of activity in each lesson. They were also required to give reflection about the lessons and activity, the challenges they experience, learning acquired and application of the lesson/activity in everyday life. This was done in a portfolio format.

Procedure

Before the start of the study, the researcher informs the learners that one of their interventions or enhancement activities was grounded in research on the topic matter. The researcher introduced the reflective portfolio as an augmentation activity for their General Biology class. It's going to be an extra task and a way to build on what they've learned.

The researchers conducted a pre-test on the respondents before the discussion of the lessons. This was undertaken to determine the levels of knowledge of the participants on selected lessons in Biology. The 40-item examination runs for almost 40 minutes since the time allotment for the subject is 4 hours per week. The researcher met four times a week. One hour was also allocated to discuss the research, the purpose, and the intervention.

The result of the participants in their pre-test and post-test consisted the raw data for quantitative analysis. The gathered data were subjected to statistical treatment using SPSS. The researchers made a table that showed the result of the level of knowledge as manifested by the students before and after the conduct of the intervention using a reflective portfolio in teaching and learning the subjects.

Data Analysis

To answer the problem, gathered data were examined using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 with an alpha set at 0.05. Data results were shown through the table where it was noted the level of knowledge as manifested by the learners before and after the conduct of instruction using the reflective portfolio as part of their activity. Data were gathered through a 40-item multiple-choice test questionnaire.

Statistical Tools. The data obtained in this study were tallied, processed, and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 22 with alpha set at .05. This action research sought the help of an expert to present the results and findings of the study. The researcher used mean and t-tests for dependent samples to analyze the data for the results of before and after the discussion.

Thematic Analysis. The qualitative data gathered from observations and responses from the interview and FGD were subjected to thematic analysis. This is an analysis method that involves reading through a data set and identifying patterns in meaning across the data to derive themes.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the pretest and posttest results of the participants before and after the conduct of the intervention. The STEM strand in senior high school is an inquiry and research-based program. It exposes students to more complex mathematics and science concepts and aims to serve as a foundation for their future college degrees. It encompasses many subject matters compared with other SHS strands. The subject of General Biology is being taught in senior high school as one of the specialized subjects of Science and Technology, Mathematics, and Engineering in two parts. General Biology 1 subject is designed to enhance the understanding of the principles and concepts in the study of biology, particularly life processes at the cellular and molecular levels. It also covers the transformation of energy in organisms. General Biology 2 is designed to enhance the understanding of the principles and concepts in the study of Biology, particularly of heredity and variation, and the diversity of living organisms, their structure, function, and evolution. This study covers Cell Theory and Cell Structure and Function topics in General Biology 1.

Table 1. *Results of Pre-test and Post-test of the Participants in General Biology Subject*

	Mean	Sd	Description
Pre-test (Before)	17.85	4.89	Average
Post-test (After)	26.00	6.10	High

Legend: 32.01 – 40.00 (Very High); 24.01 – 32.00 (High); 16.01 – 24.00 (Average); 8.01 -16.00 (Low); 0.00 – 8.00 (Very Low)

The data revealed that before the instruction using the reflective portfolio in teaching biology topics. Their score on the pre-test was average ($M = 17.85$, $SD = 4.89$). After the implementation of the intervention using the reflective portfolio, the post-test showed a high ($M=26.00$, $SD=6.10$) result. The results revealed that the learners have a good foundation in Biology topics since the basic knowledge with regards to the given topic (Cell Theory and Cell Structure and Function) was already taught in junior high school (JHS), thus the average result. Also, inclination toward science could be the reason for having a good foundation since they prefer STEM as their strand in senior high school and were expected to be good in science subjects like Biology.

Table 2. Paired Sample *t*-test Results in the Difference in the Level of Understanding Manifested by the Learners Before and After the Conduct of Reflective Portfolio

	Mean	Sd	t	df	Sig.
Pre-test and Post-test	-8.15	6.45	-7.995	39	.000

$p < 0.05$

Table 2 displayed the paired sample *t*-test results in the difference in the test scores of the participants before and after the intervention.

Paired sample *t*-test results for the test scores of the participants on the pre-test and post-test showed that there is a significant difference in the level of understanding manifested by the learners before and after the conduct of the implementation ($t(39) = -7.995$ $p < .005$), hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Additionally, the negative *t*-value indicates an increase in scores from the pre-test and post-test. This means that students have learned and enhanced their understanding during the conduct of this study using a reflective portfolio.

The study's findings are consistent with those of Pennbrant, Nunstedt, and Bernhardsson (2019), who claimed that students can improve their capacity for making thoughtful, balanced decisions when organizing tasks for work-integrated learning with the use of the portfolio technique. To assess the effects of different activities, one must possess strong self-regulation as well as the capacity for meta-cognition and methodical meta-reflection. The portfolio approach can also help students think more deeply, enhance their capacity for self-learning, highlight their talents, and accomplish more learning objectives in higher education. Furthermore, according to them systematic reflection can be an activity that supports students in developing their knowledge and abilities, learning through ongoing feedback, access to course material, and chances to practice independent thought and learning responsibility.

The study's findings are consistent with those of Lyons and Freidus (2004), who argue that a reflective portfolio process can offer an extremely approachable framework that supports practitioner inquiries, disseminates practice knowledge, and invites discussion to develop new scholarship in teacher education.

Based on the qualitative analysis of data from FGD, interview, and observation the following themes were generated:

Encourage Critical Thinking

Reflective portfolios encourage critical thinking in learners since it help them organize their thoughts, apply what is being criticized to them, relate or connect theory to practice, develop metacognitive abilities, and participate in self-evaluation. This helped them in problem solving and to be confident in making informed decision by continuous practice of reflection and analysis. According to participants 3, 4, 10, 24, 31, and 35, "Through reflective portfolio we are encouraged to think and analyze what we have experience, what we think and do". Also, participants 6, 14, 26, 29, 31, and 38, "It made us examine if our way of thinking or what we did is correct or not".

Promotes Deeper Understanding

A reflective portfolio requires students to actively participate in their education, make connections between their theoretical knowledge and real-world applications, and continually improve their understanding through feedback and reflection. It does this by encouraging active participation, bridging theory and practice, promoting ongoing reflection, cultivating metacognitive abilities, incorporating feedback, and bolstering evidence-based self-evaluation. Students can comprehend their subject matter and their learning processes on a deeper, more nuanced level thanks to this all-encompassing approach. According to participants 7, 8, 15, 19, 25, 37, and 44 "This activity it made us think deeper, not just think superficial knowledge." Participants 12, 22, 28, 23, 32, and 36 furthered that "Using this approach made us connect what we have learned to exist ideas or examples around us (example, technologies)".

Encourages Problem-Solving Skills

By utilizing self-evaluation, reflection, and application, feedback to aid problem-solving is made possible through portfolio implements. With this, students can easily identify problems, conceptualize approaches, and develop a well-improved project. Through the portfolio, learners can easily apply theoretical knowledge, make them even more creative, accept corrections/criticisms for improvement, boost students' development in metacognitive and planning skills, and be more resilient and confident. Students are provided with the tools and perspective necessary to effectively address problems in both academic and real-world contexts with the aid of this comprehensive approach. Participants 2, 7, 13, 22, 33, and 31 stated that "With the use of reflection in our activity we can freely think of what solution can be done to a particular problem". According to participants 5, 9, 11, 21, 27, 36, and 40, "By reflecting, I can think freely appropriate solutions in a problem that we are trying to reflect on".

Increase Learners Engagement

Reflective portfolios can improve learner engagement by enhancing interactivity, personalization, and significance of the learning process. This makes the learners to be more participative by personalizing the learning process, establishing their goals, and self-improvement. Portfolios also encouraged learners to think actively and think critically, encouraging feedback, interaction creativity, and real-world experiences. These components work together to produce a learning environment that is more participatory, meaningful, and engaging. According to participants 5, 8, 26, 28, 31, and 39, "Since we are answering at our phase, it creates opportunities for us for active learning and self-expression, since this activity was done individually". As for participants 3, 13, 16, 26, 27, 31, and 40 "Activities like this can be done by groups. Thus, can encourage participation". Also, participant 8, 17, 27, 24, and 37 further, "This is an avenue for collaboration since we can share our thoughts with others and at the same time listen to their thoughts also".

Reflection has been proven to be a significant tool in the teaching and learning process. The result of the study agrees with the idea of the experiential learning paradigm which emphasizes that reflection is important in helping learners use what they learned to create abstract ideas from real-world experiences (Kolb, 1984). The results of the study are in agreement with other studies related to reflective learning. In the study of Larsen, London, and Emke (2016), reflection can be used to "influence students' learning from experience, increase their awareness of their thoughts and actions, and increase their perceived recall of experiences." Students' retention of experience is strengthened when they undertake reflections because they regularly access the knowledge from memory. To evaluate their professional work and demonstrate their tangible practice, learners can build portfolios. According to Birrill and Addison (2010), the reflective remarks expected in teaching portfolios are articulations of identity in practice and negotiations of the repertoires of the community. According to Gausdal (2008), using reflection as a tool for student learning enables learners to create and share local explicit and tacit knowledge. Researchers reflected on their experience in writing a variety of formats, including journals, summaries, and portfolios (Roskos, Vukelich, & Risko, 2001). They concluded that learners could arrive at deeper concepts through interactive reflection.

Students get the chance to record their educational path and offer recommendations and references for upcoming learners. In the study of Helyer (2015), learners who make use of reflection will make them learn better and develop their talents further. This qualitative study is comparable to the result of Chang (2019) who identified five themes as to how reflection influences learning. These are: deepening one's understanding; identifying areas of knowledge that are incomplete, contextualizing or being creative, personalizing knowledge, and offering learning comparisons.

The result of the study also agrees with Kob (1984) in his experiential learning paradigm. He emphasizes that reflection is important in helping learners use what they learned and create abstract ideas out of this. The results are also consistent with other studies in using reflective learning. For example, in the study of Larsen, London, and Emke (2016), reflection is a promising tool in teaching and learning since it can be used to encourage learners' learning from experience and increase their awareness of their thoughts and actions" Students' retention of experience is strengthened when they undertake reflections because they regularly access the knowledge from memory. To evaluate their professional work and demonstrate their tangible practice, learners can build portfolios. According to Birrill and Addison (2010), the reflective remarks expected in teaching portfolios are articulations of identity in practice and negotiations of the repertoires of the community. According to Gausdal (2008), using reflection on student learning enables the participants to create and share local explicit and tacit knowledge." Researchers reflected on the experience in writing a variety of formats, including journals, summaries, and portfolios (Roskos, Vukelich, & Risko, 2001). They concluded that learners could arrive at deeper concepts through interactive reflection. They further advised educators to create lesson plans that support students' growth in reflective thinking. Students get the chance to record their educational path and offer recommendations and references for upcoming learners. In the study of Helyer (2015), learners who make use of reflection will make them learn better and develop their talents further. This qualitative study is comparable to the result of Chang (2019) who identified five themes as to how reflection influences learning. These are: deepening one's understanding; identifying areas of knowledge that are incomplete, contextualizing or being creative, personalizing knowledge, and offering learning comparisons.

Conclusions

The findings of the study are an addition to the literature that supports reflective portfolios are effective teaching tool that contributes significantly to student's learning. This strengthens the notion that it is one of the effective strategies for improving the performance of learners in a particular subject. Positive attitude among learners was observed in using reflective portfolios as part of their learning activities. The result further showed that learners had an opportunity to consider the various learning tactics, experiences, and abilities that might be helpful in the future. It was also mentioned that it is an excellent tool that can be utilized in any subject, particularly biology.

Utilizing this activity as an intervention may prepare learners by offering a planned and adaptable framework for further academic development as a lifelong learner. Findings from the interview showed that there are a lot of advantages in using reflection in classroom instruction. The learners have a clear outlook on introspection and self-evaluation. It encourages them further to think critically in analyzing their outputs or work. This intervention motivates the learner further to challenge themselves, to be keener on facts, and to think of other ways other than the usual by reflecting on their learning experiences.

Using this approach also develops a mindset that values skepticism and inquiry—two qualities that are crucial to critical thinking. By using these reflective portfolios, learners can think outside the box, which is frequently defined by rote memorization and short-term memory recall. On the other hand, a reflective portfolio also encourages learners to establish connections between old and new information, which results in a greater comprehension of the subject matter.

Learners examine how they approach situations and identify their strengths and weaknesses through regular reflection. Through this approach, a growth of mentality will be maintained, and resilience are encouraged. Students develop problem-solving skills and adapt different viewpoints by keeping track of their learning experiences and criticisms. Additionally, this approach promotes metacognition. Reflective portfolios make learners recognize and modify what they think to solve problems more effectively.

Active participation is also one of the positive outcomes of using reflective portfolios which also raises learner engagement. Regular reflection personalizes learning and meaningfully enhances learning. This will make them aware of their development and growth and motivate them to do better especially if they keep track of their accomplishment and failures. Reflective portfolios help learners by establishing connections with the subject content by having them connect what they've learned from real-world situations. Lastly, the interventions will be more effective if it will be used frequently as educational tools. With this, learners will be aware of the current level of knowledge they have acquired in a certain course, grow more as independent learners, and have more control of their academic endeavors.

Finally, the study concludes that reflective portfolios serve as an effective pedagogical tool in biology instruction, fostering a deeper understanding of the subject matter and promoting continuous improvement in the learning practices.

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